

Studies in the Naphthathiazole Series. Part I. The Constitution of the Bromo-addition Compounds of Bromo-substituted Alkylamino- β -naphthathiazoles Obtained in the Bromination of *s*- α -Naphthylalkyl thiocarbamides.

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In view of the manner in which the different syntheses of benzthiazole derivatives have been exploited by chemical investigators to both academic and technical ends, it appears curious that the study of the naphthalene homologues of these compounds has previously attracted comparatively little attention. Derivatives of α - and β -naphthathiazoles (I and II respectively) were first obtained by Hofmann in 1887 by the thionation of certain naphthalides (*Ber.*, 1887, 20, 1798), and in the same year, Jacobson prepared 2-methyl- β -naphthathiazole by oxidation of an alkaline solution of thioacet- α -naphthalide with potassium ferricyanide (*ibid.*, p. 1895). In the following year, the isomeric methyl- α -naphthathiazole was synthesised by the same reaction (Jacobson and Sullwald, *Ber.*, 1888, 21, 2624), and the 1-thiol- α - and 2-thiol- β -naphthathiazoles were subsequently prepared by Jacobson and Frankenbacher three years later (*Ber.*, 1891, 24, 1400) by heating the corresponding naphthylthiocarbimides with sulphur.

With the exception of the synthesis of certain aminonaphthathiazole derivatives (Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2270 ; 1926, 1385, and later) and the investigation of the cyanine dyes derived from quaternary salts of the methylnaphthathiazoles (Hamer, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2598), however, there has been little develop-

ment in the chemistry of the naphthathiazole group in the last forty years. The object of the present series of papers is therefore to study the unsaturation and tautomeric mobility of heterocyclic compounds of naphthathiazole derivatives, on lines similar to those which are being followed in the investigation of benzthiazole derivatives (Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 125 ; Hunter and Jones, *ibid.*, p. 2190 ; Dyson, Hunter, Jones and Styles, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 147).

In an earlier investigation it was observed that the interaction of an equimolecular proportion of bromine with a solution of a *s*- α -naphthylalkylthiocarbamide (III) in chloroform gives rise to a hydrobromide of the corresponding 2-alkylamino- β -naphthathiazole (IV) (Dyson, Hunter and Morris, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 2282), whereas bromination under the usual conditions of thiazole cyclisation (Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2023, and later) leads to the production of bromo-addition compounds of bromo-substitution derivatives. These bromo-addition compounds have now been shown to be *hydroperbromides* of the corresponding 8-bromo-2-alkylamino- β -naphthathiazoles (V) by their preparation from the corresponding *s*-4-bromo- α -naphthylalkylthiocarbamides (VI), which were synthesised from 4-bromo- α -naphthylthiocarbimide obtained from 4-bromo- α -naphthylamine and thiocarbonyl chloride in the usual way (Dyson, George and Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 3041; 1927, 436).

The bromination of *s*- α -naphthylmethylthiocarbamide in the presence of a large excess of the halogen gives rise to a highly

unstable *hydropentabromide* of 8-bromo-2-methylamino- β -naphthathiazole (V, R=Me ; $n=5$),* which is also obtained from the 4-bromonaphthylmethylthiocarbamide (VI, R=Me), under similar conditions. Bromination in the presence of a lower concentration of bromine gives rise to a *hydrotribromide* of the bromomethylamino-naphthathiazole (V, R=Me ; $n=3$), which can also be prepared by degradation of the *hydropentabromide* in a vacuum over potassium hydroxide, and by bromination of *s*-4-bromo- α -naphthylmethylthiocarbamide in the presence of a concentration of the halogen lower than that required for the production of the unstable *hydropentabromide*. As might be anticipated, this *hydrotribromide* regenerates the *hydropentabromide* on bromination in chloroform.

On bromination in chloroform in the presence of a concentration of bromine still lower than that required for the production of the *hydrotribromide*, *s*- α -naphthylmethylthiocarbamide yielded a yellow-orange *hydrodibromide* of the 8-bromomethylaminonaphthathiazole base, which was also obtained by degradation of the *hydrotribromide* in a desiccator containing potassium hydroxide. This substance, which was the most stable of the three bromo-addition compounds under ordinary laboratory conditions, is evidently analogous to the *hydrodibromide* of 1-aminobenzthiazole (Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 125) and probably contains a Br_2 ion, whose formulation involves the operation of a lone singlet linkage (*cf.* Hunter, *Chem. and Ind.*, 1932, 51, 939).

s- α -Naphthylethylthiocarbamide behaved similarly to the methylthiocarbamide and gave rise to a *hydropentabromide*, a *hydrotribromide*, or a *hydrodibromide* of 8-bromo-2-ethylamino- β -naphthathia-

* This formulation is not necessarily meant to imply the existence of a Br_5 ion in highly unstable compounds of this type. The bromine which is so readily eliminated from the *hydropentabromide* of 8-bromo-2-methylamino- β -naphthathiazole with the production of the more stable *hydrotribromide*, for instance, may possibly be present in the form of a physical mixture, the solid phase of which has the composition, $[\text{Base}, \text{H}] \text{Br}_3, \text{Br}_2$ (*cf.* Dyson, Hunter, Jones and Styles, *loc. cit.*). The seat of the phenomenon of polybromide formation of this type is, however, the bromine ion of the *hydrobromide* of the base produced by thiazole cyclisation (Hunter, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 435), and it is reasonable to assume that the affinity which leads to the production of a *hydrotribromide* complex will be relayed, in some measure at least, through the bromine atoms of the Br_3 ion.

zole, according to the conditions of the reaction. The hydrotribromide was also obtained from the hydropentabromide by loss of bromine as in the case of the methyl derivative. The constitution of these bromo-addition compounds was established by synthesis from *s*-4-bromo- α -naphthylethylthiocarbamide as in the previous case.

The bromination of *s*- α -naphthyl-*iso*-amylthiocarbamide was also re-examined, and it was observed that this thiocarbamide gave rise to a *hydropentabromide* or a *hydrodibromide* of the 8-bromo-2-*iso*-amylamino base, according to the conditions of the experiment. This hydropentabromide was also prepared from the 4-bromo- α -naphthyl-*iso*-amylthiocarbamide by treatment with a considerable excess of the halogen, and yielded the hydrotribromide by loss of a molecule of bromine as in the case of the methyl and ethyl compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The *s*- α -naphthylalkylthiocarbamides are much more conveniently prepared by condensation of α -naphthylthiocarbimide and the corresponding alkylamine than by condensation of α -naphthylamine with the requisite alkylthiocarbimides (Dyson and Hunter, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1926, 45, 421; Dyson, Hunter and Soyka, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 129, 2964). Considerable difficulty was experienced in preparing α -naphthylthiocarbimide by the methods given in the literature. It was most readily obtained from *s*-di- α -naphthylthiocarbamide and boiling acetic anhydride by the method used for the preparation of the β -isomer (Hunter and Jones, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 942), but the yield was always poor (10 to 20 per cent). The thiocarbimide was also prepared by adding α -naphthylamine (1 mol.) in chloroform (5 vols.) to a well-stirred suspension of thiocarbonyl chloride (1.3 mols.) in water (10 vols.) at laboratory temperature; stirring being continued for a further 30 minutes after the completion of the addition of the amine solution, and the thiocarbimide isolated in the usual way (Dyson, George and Hunter, *loc. cit.*).

8-Bromo-2-methylamino- β -naphthathiazole hydropentabromide (V, R=Me; $n=5$).—(i) *Bromination of s- α -Naphthylmethylthiocarbamide*. A solution of the naphthylmethylthiocarbamide (m.p. 198°) in chloroform (0.2 g. in 4 c.c.) was treated with bromine (0.8 c.c. in 0.7 c.c. of the same solvent) and the mixture was heated under reflux on a water-bath for 5 minutes. The hydropentabromide finally separated in orange-red rhombic crystals which were transferred to

porous earthenware, placed in a vacuum desiccator which was rapidly exhausted on an oil pump, and the crystals analysed with the usual precautions (Dyson, Hunter and Soyka, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 458) after one or two minutes. [Found: Br (total), 70·0; Br (labile), 45·3. $C_{12}H_9N_2BrS$, $HBr(Br_4)$ requires Br (total), 69·1; Br (labile), 46·1 per cent]. Just after the moment of its isolation the bromo-addition compound had m. p. 135° (decomp.), but this rose to 163° (decomp.), which is the m.p. of the hydrotribomide, after a lapse of 10 minutes (Dyson, Hunter and Soyka, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 2964, recorded this for the m.p. of the supposed "hexabromide of 2-methylamino- β -naphthathiazole"). On reduction with sulphurous acid and sulphur dioxide, and basification with ammonia (d 0·880), the hydro-pentabromide yielded 8-bromo-2-methylamino- β -naphthathiazole, which crystallised from alcohol-ethyl acetate (animal charcoal) in aggregates of small needles, m.p. 194-95°, identical with the specimen synthesised from 4-bromo- α -naphthylthiocarbimide by way of *s*-4-bromo- α -naphthylmethylthiocarbamide. (Found: Br, 27·2, $C_{12}H_9N_2BrS$ requires Br, 27·3 per cent). The *acetyl* derivative, obtained by boiling a solution of 8-bromo-2-methylamino- β -naphthathiazole in acetic anhydride for a few minutes and diluting the solution with alcohol, separated from alcohol in microscopic needles, m.p. 208°. (Found: Br, 24·2. $C_{14}H_{11}ON_2BrS$ requires Br, 23·8 per cent).

(ii) *Synthesis from 4-Bromo- α -naphthylthiocarbimide by way of s-4-Bromo- α -naphthylmethylthiocarbamide.* 4-Bromo- α -naphthylthiocarbimide.—A solution of 4-bromo- α -naphthylamine (9 g.) in chloroform (60 c.c.) was gradually added to a mechanically stirred suspension of thiocarbonyl chloride (9 c.c.) in water (60 c.c.) in the course of 20 minutes, and vigorous stirring was continued for a further 10 minutes. The sticky product was separated and kept overnight in a desiccator containing sulphuric acid and extracted with boiling benzene in which the dibromo-dinaphthyl-thiocarbamide which was formed as a by-product was practically insoluble. The *thiocarbimide* crystallised from this solvent in small thick needles, m.p. 90°. (Found: Br, 30·0. $C_{11}H_6NBrS$ requires Br, 30·3 per cent) *s*-4-Bromo- α -naphthylmethylthiocarbamide. A suspension of the naphthylthiocarbimide (1 g.) in alcohol (10 c.c.) was treated with a 33 per cent solution of methylamine (1·6 c.c.), when the thiocarbimide dissolved on warming, giving a dark brown solution which was concentrated. The crystals of the methylthiocarbamide thus obtained

were washed with methyl alcohol to remove the coloured impurity, and had m.p. 179°. (Found: Br, 27.0. $C_{12}H_{11}N_2BrS$ requires Br, 27.1 per cent). A solution of the bromonaphthylmethylthiocarbamide (0.2 g.) in chloroform (5 c.c.) was treated with bromine (0.6 c.c. in 1 c.c. of the same solvent) and the mixture was heated on a water bath under reflux for 5 minutes. The hydropentabromide obtained in this way had m.p. 136° after rapid drying in vacuum. [Found: Br (total), 70.1; Br (labile), 46.0 per cent], and yielded 8-bromo-2-methylamino- β -naphthathiazole on reduction, which had m.p. 194° alone, and when mixed with the specimen already described.

8-Bromo-2-methylamino- β -naphthathiazole hydrotribromide (V, R=Me; $n=3$).—(i) *Bromination of s- α -Naphthylmethylthiocarbamide*. The naphthylmethylthiocarbamide (0.2 g.) in chloroform (4 c.c.) was treated with bromine (0.6 c.c. in 0.6 c.c. of chloroform) and the mixture was heated on a water bath for 5 minutes. A yellow precipitate first separated which acquired a pinkish colour, which was dried on porous earthenware in a vacuum. The *hydrotribromide* formed pink needles, m.p. 162-64° (decomp. blackening at 115-125°). [Found: Br (total), 60.0; Br (labile), 29.1. $C_{12}H_9N_2BrS$, HBr (Br₂) requires Br (total), 60.0; Br(labile), 30.0 per cent].

(ii) *Degradation of the hydropentabromide of 8-Bromo-2-methylamino- β -naphthathiazole*. The hydropentabromide of the 8-bromo-naphthathiazole was kept in a vacuum over potassium hydroxide, when the red crystals decomposed with loss of bromine yielding crystals of the hydrotribromide m.p. 162.163°. [Found: Br (total), 61.4; Br (labile), 29.9 per cent].

(iii) *Preparation from s-4-Bromo- α -naphthylmethylthiocarbamide and Bromine*. A solution of the bromonaphthylthiocarbamide in chloroform (0.2 g. in 5 c.c.) was treated with bromine (0.4 c.c. in 0.7 c.c. of the same solvent), and the mixture was heated for 5 minutes under reflux when the hydrotribromide was obtained, m.p. 163°. [Found: Br (total), 60.9; Br (labile), 30.0 per cent]. Bromination of the hydrotribromide in chloroform solution yielded the hydropentabromide of 8-bromo-2-methylamino- β -naphthathiazole which was identified by its appearance, m.p. and analysis [Found: Br (total), 69.3; Br (labile), 46.0 per cent].

8-Bromo-2-methylamino- β -naphthathiazole hydrodibromide.—A solution of s- α -naphthylmethylthiocarbamide (0.6 g.) in chloroform (20 c.c.) was treated with bromine (1.2 c.c.) and the mixture was

heated for 5 minutes, when the *hydrodibromide* was obtained in the form of fine orange yellow needles, m.p. 195° (decomp.). [Found: Br (total), 52.9; Br (labile), 17.6. $C_{12}H_9N_2BrS$, $HBr(Br)$ requires Br (total), 52.9; Br (labile), 17.6 per cent]. This compound was the most stable of these three bromo-addition compounds and was also obtained by keeping the hydrotribromide in a desiccator over potassium hydroxide for 4 days. The specimen obtained in this way had m.p. 197°. [Found: Br (total), 52.4; Br (labile), 17.4 per cent].

8-Bromo-2-ethylamino-β-naphthathiazole *hydropentabromide*
(V,R=Et; n=5) (i) *Bromination of s-α-Naphthylethylthiocarbamide*. A solution of *s-α-naphthylethylthiocarbamide* (m.p. 124°) in chloroform (0.2 g. in 4 c.c.) was treated with bromine (0.6 c.c. in 0.8 c.c. of chloroform) and the mixture was heated for 6 minutes on a water bath under reflux, and then concentrated under reduced pressure at laboratory temperature. The orange-red *hydropentabromide* was obtained, m.p. 93°. [Found: Br (total), 67.8; Br (labile), 45.0. $C_{13}H_{11}N_2BrS$, $HBr(Br_4)$ requires Br (total), 67.7; Br (labile), 45.2 per cent]. On reduction with sulphurous acid and sulphur dioxide it yielded *8-bromo-2-ethylamino-β-naphthathiazole* which crystallised from alcohol-ethyl acetate in soft silky needles, m.p. 147°. (Found: Br, 10.0. $C_{13}H_{11}N_2BrS$ requires Br, 10.1 per cent). The *acetyl* derivative, prepared by heating a solution of the base in acetic anhydride for a few minutes and diluting with alcohol, crystallised in colourless prisms, m.p. 172-73°. (Found: S, 9.2. $C_{15}H_{13}ON_2BrS$ requires S, 8.8 per cent).

(ii) *Synthesis from s-4-Bromo-α-naphthylethylthiocarbamide*. *s-4-Bromo-α-naphthylethylthiocarbamide*. The gum obtained by concentrating a mixture of 4-bromo- $\bar{\alpha}$ -naphthylthiocarbimide (1g.) in alcohol (10 c.c.) and ethylamine (1.6 c.c. of a 33 per cent solution in water) was kept overnight, and then triturated with ether, when it solidified. The ethylthiocarbamide could not, however, be obtained crystalline and had m.p. 82° after being washed free from gummy impurities by ether. (Found: Br, 25.0. $C_{13}H_{13}N_2BrS$ requires Br, 25.8 per cent). A solution of this product in chloroform (0.2 g. in 4 c.c.) was treated with bromine (0.8 c.c. in 0.5 c.c. of chloroform) and the mixture was concentrated in a vacuum after being heated under reflux for 5 minutes. The crystals of the *hydropentabromide* obtained in this way were brown coloured, due evidently to an impurity in the bromonaphthylethylthiocarbamide, but had similar properties to those of the specimen already described,

m.p. 94°. [Found: Br (total), 67·7; Br (labile), 45·1 per cent]. On reduction with sulphurous acid, it yielded 8-bromo-2-ethylamino- β -naphthathiazole, which was undepressed by admixture with the specimen already described.

8-Bromo-2-ethylamino- β -naphthathiazole hydrotribromide. (i) *Bromination of s- α -Naphthylethylthiocarbamide.* A solution of the naphthylethylthiocarbamide in chloroform (0·2 g. in 4 c.c.) was treated with bromine (0·6 c.c. in 0·8 c.c. of chloroform) and the mixture was heated on a water bath for 6 minutes when the *hydrotribromide* separated in yellow crystals, m.p. 204°. [Found: Br (total), 58·2; Br (labile), 29·0. $C_{13}H_{11}N_2BrS$, $HBr(Br_2)$ requires Br (total), 58·0; Br (labile), 29·1 per cent].

(ii) *Degradation of 8-Bromo-2-ethylamino- β -naphthathiazole hydropentabromide.* The hydrotribromide was also obtained by keeping the hydropentabromide in a desiccator over potassium hydroxide; the specimen obtained in this way had m.p. 203°. [Found: Br (total), 58·3; Br (labile), 29·0 per cent].

(iii) *Synthesis from s-4-Bromo- α -naphthylethylthiocarbamide.* The hydrotribromide of 8-bromo-2-ethylamino- β -naphthathiazole was also prepared as in the case of the methyl derivative by treating a solution of the bromonaphthylethylthiocarbamide (0·2 g.) in chloroform (4 c.c.) with bromine (0·7 c.c. in 0·7 c.c. of chloroform) in the usual way and identified by m.p. and analysis. [Found: Br (labile), 29·0 per cent.]. On reduction with sulphurous acid and sulphur dioxide, it yielded 8-bromo-2-ethylamino- β -naphthathiazole as in the case of the higher bromo-addition compound.

8-Bromo-2-isoamylamino- β -naphthathiazole hydropentabromide (V, $R = iso-C_5H_{11}$; $n = 5$). (i) *Bromination of s- α -Naphthylisoamylthiocarbamide.* A solution of the isoamylthiocarbamide in chloroform (0·2 g. in 4 c.c.) was treated with bromine (0·8 c.c. in 0·6 c.c. of chloroform) and the mixture was heated for 5 minutes, and the solution concentrated under reduced pressure at laboratory temperature. The *hydropentabromide* formed orange red unstable crystals which were rapidly dried on porous earthenware in vacuum and analysed; m.p. 79-80°. [Found: Br (total), 64·1; Br (labile), 42·6. $C_{16}H_{17}N_2BrS$, $HBr(Br_4)$ requires Br (total), 64·0; Br (labile), 42·6 per cent]. A specimen of the hydropentabromide kept in a weighing bottle overnight, decomposed yielding the *hydrotribromide* of 8-bromo-2-iso-amylamino- β -naphthathiazole which had m. p. 121°. [Found: Br (total), 54·3; Br (labile), 27·2. $C_{16}H_{17}N_2BrS$,

HBr (Br₂) requires Br (total), 54·2; Br (labile), 27·1 per cent]. On reduction with sulphurous acid and basification with ammonia, it yielded 8-bromo-2-isoamylamino- β -naphthathiazole which had m. p. 126° alone, and when mixed with the specimen obtained from s-4-bromo- α -naphthylisoamylthiocarbamide. (Found: Br, 22·7. C₁₆H₁₇N₂BrS requires Br, 22·9 per cent).

(ii) *Synthesis from s-4-Bromo- α -naphthylisoamylthiocarbamide.* s-4-Bromo- α -naphthyliso-amylthiocarbamide. The gum obtained by concentrating a mixture of 4-bromo- α -naphthylthiocarbamide (1 g.) and isoamylamine (0·8 c.c.) in alcohol (7 c. c.) did not solidify after being kept in a vacuum desiccator for 2 days. It was therefore triturated with ether as in the case of the bromonaphthylethyl derivative. The product obtained in this way had m. p. 128° (after sintering at 118°). (Found: Br. 22·7. C₁₆H₁₉N₂BrS requires Br, 22·7 per cent). A solution of this bromonaphthylthiocarbamide in chloroform (0·2 g. in 4·5 c. c.) was treated with bromine (0·8 c. c. in 0·5 c. c. of chloroform) and the mixture was heated for 5 minutes and concentrated in vacuum. The deep orange crystals of the hydropentabromide obtained in this way were very unstable and rapidly lost bromine yielding the more stable hydrotribromide. [Found: Br (total), 64·0; Br (labile), 42·7 per cent].

8-Bromo-2-isoamylamino- β -naphthathiazole hydrotribromide. *Bromination of s- α -Naphthylisoamylthiocarbamide.* A solution of the naphthylthiocarbamide in chloroform (0·2 g. in 4 c. c.) was treated with bromine (0·6 c. c. in 0·6 c. c. of chloroform) and the solution was heated for 5 minutes and thereafter concentrated under reduced pressure at laboratory temperature, when the hydrotribromide separated in yellow crystals, m. p. 121°. [Found: Br (total), 53·9; Br (labile), 27·0 per cent]. On reduction with sulphurous acid and basification with ammonia, it yielded 8-bromo-2-isoamylamino- β -naphthathiazole which was identified in the usual way.

